

**“CHOOSE WITH CARE”: AN ANALYSIS OF THE TRANSLATION
OF RACIST SLANG AND NON-SLANG TERMS SUCH AS “BLACK”,
“DARKIE”, “NIGGER”, AND “NEGRO” INTO TURKISH
IN ANDREA LEVY’S “SMALL ISLAND”**

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This paper analyzes the translation of racist slang and non-slang terms, including “Black,” “Darkie,” “Nigger,” and “Negro” into Turkish in Andrea Levy’s novel *Small Island* (2004) to show the complexities of translating the concepts that do not have Turkish equivalents and the significance of the translator’s endeavour to preserve the emotional, historical and cultural value of the original text. In *Small Island*, Andrea Levy (1956-2019) depicts the interconnected lives of four characters - two Jamaicans, Hortense and Gilbert, and two Britons, Queenie and Bernard - grappling with themes of race, identity, and post-World War II immigration in England. For the racist comments in the novel, the words “Black,” “Darkie,” “Nigger,” and “Negro” are used, each carrying a distinct degree of offensiveness. However, these racist phrases, such as “Darkie,” “Nigger,” and “Negro,” which have a unique racial history in English, lack obvious Turkish equivalents because for the word “Black,” only two words, “siyahi” and “zenci,” which do not have offensive meanings compared to English, are used. The aim of this paper is, thus, to present how the translator, who

does not pay attention to their usage in both languages, employs them arbitrarily throughout the translation process, regardless of the context. This approach fails to demonstrate the intended level of offensiveness in the original text and fails to accurately convey the same depth of meaning.